

Studies in Quinazolines. Part IV : Synthesis of 2-Alkyl-3-Alkyl Aralkyl/Aryl-4(3H)-Benzo(g) quinazolinones and 2-Mercapto-3-Aryl alkyl/alkyl-4-(3H)-Benzo(g) quinazolinones.

P. S. SATPANTHI & J. P. TRIVEDI

Chemistry Department, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-9

Received 4 November 1968; revised MSS received 9 September 1971

Several 2-alkyl-3-alkyl/aralkyl/aryl and 2-mercapto-3-aralkyl/alkyl/aryl-4(3H)benzo(g) quinazolinones have been synthesized for studying their physiological properties. These compounds have been prepared from 2-amino-3-naphthoic acid and the appropriate amine of isothiocyanates. Some of these have been characterised through their S-methyl derivatives.

Linear benzoquinazolinones are not studied in details and relatively few workers have worked with them. Of the few known important linear benzo(g)quinazolinones substituted in the pyrimidine ring are 4-chloro, 4-amino, 4-hydroxy and 2,4-dihydroxy compounds¹. Aggarwal, Das and Ray² have prepared 2-benzyl-4(3H)-benzo(g)-quinazolinones. Etinne and Legrand³ have prepared 4(3H)-benzo(g)quinazolinones. Reid and Stephan⁴ prepared 4(3H)-benzo(g)quinazolinones of the type I (where R₂ is EtOOC.CH₂, -CH₂CN, -CH₂CH₂CN, -(CH₂)₃CN, CH₃, -CH₂Ph and R₁ is H). 4-Quinazolinones have been patented as bronchodilators⁵. With a view to study their physiological properties several 2-alkyl-3-alkyl/aralkyl/aryl-4(3H)-benzo(g)quinazolinones (I) and 2-mercapto-3-aralkyl/alkyl/aryl-4(3H)-benzo(g)quinazolinones (II) have been synthesised and reported in the present paper.

where R₁ = *n*-butyl, C₆H₅, 2-CH₃OC₆H₄-, 4-CH₃OC₆H₄-, 2-, 3- and 4-CH₃C₆H₄-, 4-BrC₆H₄-, 4-IC₆H₄-, 2-, 3- and 4-NO₂C₆H₄-, C₆H₅CH₂-, α - and β -C₁₀H₇ and R₂ = CH₃ and C₂H₅.

where R₁ = H or CH₃ and R₂ = C₆H₅-, 2-, 3- and 4-ClC₆H₄-, 2-, 3- and 4-CH₃C₆H₄-, 2- and 4-CH₃OC₆H₄-, 4-BrC₆H₄-, 4-IC₆H₄-, C₆H₅CH₂-, 2-, 3- and 4-ClC₆H₄CH₂-, 2-, 3- and 4-CH₃C₆H₄CH₂-, 4-BrC₆H₄CH₂-, 2,4-, 2,5- and 3,4-(CH₃)₂C₆H₃CH₂-, 2,4-Cl₂C₆H₃CH₂-, *n*-butyl, *n*-amyl, *n*-hexyl.

Compounds (I) were synthesised through N-acyl derivatives of 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid and appropriate amines using phosphorous trichloride or oxychloride as a condensing agent⁶. Table 1 describes the compounds thus prepared.

TABLE 1

2-Alkyl-3-Alkyl/Aryl/Aralkyl-4-(3H)-Benzo(g)quinazolines

R ₂	R ₁	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % N	
				Found	Calcd.
CH ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	232-35	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	10.4	10.5
"	C ₆ H ₅	104-05	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	9.7	9.8
"	4',CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	206-08	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	8.9	8.9
"	2',CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	170	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	9.2	9.3
"	2',CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	199	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	8.8	8.9
"	3',CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	141	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	9.1	9.3
"	4',CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	200	-do-	9.2	9.3
"	2',ClC ₆ H ₄	207	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O	8.7	8.8
"	4',ClC ₆ H ₄	200	-do-	8.6	8.8
"	4',BrC ₆ H ₄	203	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O	7.6	7.7
"	4',IC ₆ H ₄	218	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ IN ₂ O	7.0	7.1
"	2',NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	257	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃	12.6	12.7
"	3',NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	223	-do-	12.5	12.7
"	4',NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	243	-do-	12.6	12.7
"	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	68	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	9.2	9.3
"	1',C ₁₀ H ₇	220	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	8.0	8.3
"	2',C ₁₀ H ₇	185	-do-	8.1	8.3
C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	192-94	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	9.2	9.3
"	4',CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	255	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	8.3	8.5
"	2',CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	207	-do-	8.4	8.5
"	2',CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	231	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	8.8	8.9
"	3',CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	208-10	-do-	8.7	8.9
"	4',CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	190	-do-	8.8	8.9
"	4',ClC ₆ H ₄	202	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O	8.3	8.4
"	2',ClC ₆ H ₄	226	-do-	8.2	8.4
"	4',BrC ₆ H ₄	221	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ O	7.2	7.4
"	4',IC ₆ H ₄	229	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ IN ₂ O	6.4	6.6
"	3',NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	180	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃	12.0	12.2
"	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	153	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	8.7	8.9
"	2',C ₁₀ H ₇	169	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	7.9	8.0

All of the above compounds crystallised from methyl ethyl ketone; nitrogen determination was performed according to the standard Kjeldahl's method.

TABLE 2(A)

2-Thio-3-substituted-4(3H)-benzo(g)quinazolinones

R ₁	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % N	
			Found	Calcd.
<i>n</i> -CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₅	256	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS	8.9	9.0
S-methyl of above	115	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ OS	8.5	8.6
<i>n</i> -CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₄	246	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	9.3	9.4
S-methyl of above	117	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS	8.8	9.0

The above compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE 2(B)

2-Mercapto-3-Aryl/Aralkyl-4(3H)-benzo(g)quinazolinones

R ₁	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % N	
			Found	Calcd.
H	298	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	12.0	12.1
S-methyl	230	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	11.3	11.4
2'-Cl	286	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS	10.1	10.2
S-methyl	220	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ OS	9.9	10.0
3'-Cl	331	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS	10.1	10.2
S-methyl	225	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ OS	9.9	10.0
4'-Cl	330	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS	10.2	10.2
S-methyl	223	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ OS	9.8	10.0
2'-CH ₃	290	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	11.3	11.4
S-methyl	180	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	10.7	10.8
3'-CH ₃	307	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	11.3	11.4
S-methyl	195	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	10.7	10.8
4'-CH ₃	296	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	11.3	11.4
S-methyl	192	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	10.6	10.8
2'-CH ₃ O	270	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.6	10.7
S-methyl	180	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.1	10.1
4'-CH ₃ O	299-300	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.6	10.7
S-methyl	234	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.0	10.1
4'-Br	315	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ BrN ₂ OS	8.9	9.0
S-methyl	254	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ OS	8.5	8.6

The above compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE 2(C)

2-Mercapto-3-Aralkyl-4(3H)-benzo(g)quinazolinones

R ₁	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis % N	
			Found	Calcd.
H	250	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	9.2	9.2
S-methyl	152	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	8.6	8.8
2'-Cl	265(d)	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ OS	8.1	8.2
S-methyl	165	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ OS	7.8	7.9
3'-Cl	307	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ OS	8.2	8.2
S-methyl	140	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ OS	7.8	7.9
4'-Cl	245	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ OS	8.0	8.2
S-methyl	95-96	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ OS	7.7	7.9
2'-CH ₃	290	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	8.7	8.8
S-methyl	196	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	8.2	8.4
3'-CH ₃	295	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	8.7	8.8
S-methyl	110	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	8.3	8.4
4'-CH ₃	265	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	8.6	8.8
S-methyl	158	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	8.2	8.4
4'-Br	273	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ OS	7.2	7.3
S-methyl	164	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ OS	6.9	7.0
2',4'-(CH ₃) ₂	276	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	8.4	8.4
S-methyl	169	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS	7.8	8.0
2',5'-(CH ₃) ₂	321(d)	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	8.3	8.4
S-methyl	189	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS	7.9	8.0
3',4'-(CH ₃) ₂	280	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ OS	8.3	8.4
S-methyl	157	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ OS	7.8	8.0
2',4'-Cl ₂	290	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	7.4	7.5
S-methyl	188	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	7.1	7.2

The above compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

Compounds (II) were synthesised by the condensation of 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid with the corresponding isothiocyanates in absolute ethanol as described by Trivedi⁷. The compounds thus prepared are described in Tables 2(A), 2(B) & 2(C). These on methylation gave the corresponding 2-mercaptomethyl derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Propionamido-2-naphthoic acid: This was prepared from 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid, fused sodium propionate and propionic anhydride. It was crystallised from ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 236°. (Found: N, 5.72%; C₁₄H₁₃NO₃ requires 5.76% N).

2-Alkyl-3-Alkyl/Aralkyl/Aryl-4(3H)-benzo(g)quinazolinones (I): Into a stirred mixture of 3-acylamino-2-naphthoic acid (0.21 mole), toluene (250 ml) and amine (0.20 mole) was

added a solution of phosphorous trichloride (9.2 g.; 6.0 ml) in toluene (50 ml) during fifteen minutes and the mixture refluxed in oil bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was treated with aqueous sodium carbonate and steam distilled to remove toluene. The solid obtained is washed with water and dried. The products were crystallised from suitable solvents. (Yields 50–55%).

2-Mercapto-3-Aralkyl/Alkyl/Aryl-4(3H)-benzo(g)quinazolinones (II): A mixture of 2-amino-3-naphthoic acid (0.01 mole) in absolute ethanol (40 ml) and isothiocyanate (0.01 mole) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed on a waterbath for 2 hr. In most of the cases the quinazolinones crystallised out during refluxing. In some cases the reaction time was more than 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and the crystalline solid filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. (Yield 50–65%).

Mercaptomethyl Derivatives: A mixture of above (II) (0.01 mole), anhydrous acetone (100 ml), anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g) and methyl iodide (0.01 mole) was refluxed on a waterbath for 4 hrs. Most of the acetone was distilled off and the residue treated with water. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, acetone or methyl ethyl ketone.

REFERENCES

1. E. H. Rodd, "Chemistry of Carbon Compounds", vol. IVB, pp. 1312; Elsevier, 1959.
2. J. S. Aggarwal, R. S. Das and J. N. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 717.
3. A. Etienne and M. Legrand, *Compt. rend. acad. Sci.*, 1949, **229**, 220–22.
4. W. Reid and W. Stephan, *Ber.*, 1963, **69**, 1218.
5. D. R. Mehta (Alembic Chemical Works Co. Ltd.), Indian Patent 74,424 (1963); *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, **60**, 1773.
6. Previous paper.
7. J. P. Trivedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 801.
8. W. E. Noland and D. A. Jones, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 341; H. Culbertson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4834.

